

Full-Arch Implant Rehabilitation with Titanium Bar-Supported Zirconia Hybrid Prosthesis: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Rehabilitation of partially edentulous patients with severely compromised dentition presents a significant challenge in prosthodontic treatment planning. Implant-supported fixed hybrid prostheses offer predictable functional and esthetic outcomes when conventional prosthetic options are not feasible. This case report describes the management of a patient presenting with multiple fractured teeth, root stumps, and failing prostheses in the maxillary arch. After extraction of the remaining compromised teeth, five implants were placed in the posterior regions due to insufficient anterior bone width as confirmed by cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT). Following osseointegration, a titanium bar-supported zirconia hybrid prosthesis was fabricated using digital impressions. The treatment resulted in satisfactory esthetics, function, and prosthesis fit. This case highlights the role of digital workflows and implant-supported hybrid prostheses in the rehabilitation of complex maxillary edentulous cases.

Keywords: Dental implants, Hybrid prosthesis, Zirconia prosthesis, Titanium bar, Full-arch rehabilitation, Digital prosthodontics.

INTRODUCTION

The rehabilitation of patients with severely compromised dentition often requires extraction of remaining teeth followed by implant-supported prosthetic reconstruction. Implant-supported hybrid prostheses have become a widely accepted treatment option for restoring edentulous arches, providing improved stability, function, and patient satisfaction compared with removable prostheses^[1,2]

Hybrid prostheses typically consist of a metal framework supporting acrylic or ceramic teeth, combining the advantages of fixed implant restorations with full-arch rehabilitation. Recently, titanium bar frameworks combined with zirconia restorations have gained popularity because of their superior strength, biocompatibility, and esthetic properties^[3,4]

Advanced diagnostic imaging techniques such as cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT) allow accurate evaluation of bone volume and anatomical structures, thereby facilitating appropriate implant placement and treatment planning^[4]

This case report describes the implant-supported rehabilitation of a compromised maxillary arch using five implants supporting a titanium bar-retained zirconia hybrid prosthesis.

CASE DESCRIPTION

A patient presented to the Department of Prosthodontics at CKS Teja Institute of Dental Sciences and Research, Tirupati, Andhra Pradesh, with complaints of fractured teeth and loosening of an existing prosthesis. Clinical examination following removal of the prosthesis revealed completely fractured teeth with exposed gutta-percha points and root stumps in relation to 12, 13, 14, and 15, (**Figure 1**) along with a periapical abscess associated with 22 and 23 (**Figure 3**). Teeth 24, 25, and 27 exhibited insufficient coronal tooth structure, indicating a poor prognosis for the remaining dentition. Based on these findings, extraction of the compromised teeth followed by implant-supported rehabilitation was planned. A CBCT scan was performed to evaluate bone availability, which revealed inadequate bone width in the anterior region. Consequently, implant placement in the anterior maxilla was avoided and a posterior implant-supported approach was selected.

The treatment plan included extraction of all non-restorable teeth and root stumps, followed by placement of implants in the posterior segments of the maxillary arch and fabrication of an implant-supported hybrid prosthesis. Five implants were strategically planned to achieve favorable load distribution while avoiding areas with insufficient bone volume. The implants were positioned in the first quadrant in the 15, 16, and 17 regions, and in the second quadrant in the premolar–molar and second molar regions. Under aseptic conditions, all compromised teeth were extracted and the implants were placed according to the planned distribution. A healing period of five months was allowed to facilitate osseointegration, and subsequent radiographic evaluation confirmed successful integration of the implants.

During the second-stage surgery, the cover screws were removed and healing abutments (**Figure 4**) were placed. After two weeks of soft-tissue healing, the healing abutments were replaced with multi-unit abutments (**Figure 5**) to initiate the prosthetic phase. A digital workflow was followed, where impressions were captured using an intraoral scanner with multi-unit scan bodies (**Figure 6&7**). An interim prosthesis was fabricated and evaluated for occlusal contacts, marginal adaptation, and overall fit (**Figure 8&9**). After confirming satisfactory clinical results, a titanium bar framework was fabricated and its passive fit was verified intraorally. Finally, a zirconia prosthesis was milled, pressed, and bonded to the titanium bar framework (**Figure 10&11**), providing enhanced mechanical strength, precise fit, and improved esthetics (**Figure 13&14**).

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7

Figure 8

Figure 9

Figure 10

Figure 11

Figure 12

Figure 13

Figure 14

DISCUSSION

Implant-supported prostheses have become a predictable and widely accepted treatment modality for the rehabilitation of partially or completely edentulous patients, particularly when the remaining dentition has a poor prognosis ^[1,2]. In the present case, multiple teeth exhibited severe structural damage, exposed endodontic filling material, and periapical infection, making them unsuitable for long-term retention. Extraction of the compromised teeth followed by implant-supported rehabilitation was therefore considered the most appropriate treatment approach. The use of implant-supported hybrid prostheses offers several advantages, including improved stability, enhanced masticatory efficiency, and better patient comfort when compared with conventional removable prostheses ^[1].

Preoperative assessment using Cone Beam Computed Tomography (CBCT) played a critical role in determining the treatment plan. CBCT imaging allows precise evaluation of bone height, width, and anatomical limitations, which are essential for accurate implant placement ^[4].

In this case, the

anterior maxillary region presented with insufficient bone width, making implant placement in that area unfavorable without additional augmentation procedures. To avoid invasive bone grafting procedures and reduce treatment complexity, implants were strategically placed in the posterior segments of the maxilla. Posterior implant distribution can provide favorable load distribution when properly planned and can successfully support a full-arch prosthesis ^[2].

The use of multi-unit abutments and a digital workflow significantly improved the accuracy and efficiency of the prosthetic phase. Digital impressions captured with intraoral scanners reduce the potential for errors associated with conventional impression materials and provide precise data for prosthesis fabrication. The fabrication of an interim prosthesis allowed evaluation of occlusion, esthetics, and prosthetic fit prior to the definitive restoration. Such a step is important in full-arch rehabilitations because it enables modifications before the final prosthesis is fabricated, thereby improving long-term treatment outcomes ^[4].

In the definitive prosthesis, a titanium bar framework combined with a zirconia superstructure was used. Titanium frameworks provide excellent strength, durability, and passive fit over implants, which is critical for preventing mechanical complications. Zirconia, on the other hand, offers superior esthetics, biocompatibility, and wear resistance ^[5]. The combination of a titanium bar with a zirconia prosthesis allows the clinician to benefit from both mechanical strength and esthetic superiority, making it a reliable option for implant-supported hybrid restorations.

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